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Leadership Styles and Organizational Performance: An Empirical Assessment of The Trauma and Specialist Hospital in Ghana

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Abstract

Purpose: This study examines the effect of leadership styles on organizational performance at the Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba (TSHW). Five main leadership styles were examined thus the transformational, transactional, participative, instrumental and supportive leadership styles. **Methods:** The study adopted the cross-sectional survey design. A sample size of 216 full-time employees of TSHW were selected using purposive sampling and simple random technique. Data were collected using the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ), with additional questions to evaluate the organizations performance. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation from Statistical Package for Service Solutions (SPSS) version 20. **Conclusion:** The study revealed that the most dominant leadership style at TSHW was the participative leadership style, though managers and unit heads exhibited all five leadership styles. **Implication:** It was recommended that the participative leadership style should be practised as it involves and gained the support of employees, and therefore naturally contributed to the good performance of the hospital.

Keywords: Leadership Styles, Organizational Performance, Employees, Managers, Specialist, Trauma

1. Introduction

Performance generally connotes the idea of outcome, achieved through goal and quality (Ion & Creveanu, 2016). Concerns over organizational performance play an essential role in managing organizations because of perceptions that the organization may fail. To avoid organizational failure, especially in hospitals, the onus lies on the leadership to ensure that the needs of clients seeking healthcare are accomplished both physically and psychologically as well as their social needs (Alharbi & Yusoff, 2012). Nonetheless, for every organization, performance is usually based on specific criteria to be achieved with leadership having the mandate to ensure their

achievement are met. Therefore, ensuring a successful organizational performance hinges on not only leadership but on the leadership style that is practiced at the hospital as well (Balsanelli & Cunha, 2015).

Due to the changing variables of situation and culture, leaders must always seek to introduce and implement new leadership styles which will not lower the performance of their organizations (Thuijsman, 2015). In addition, the leader must strive to get the cooperation of workers and stakeholders as a necessary prerequisite for performance (Chatterjee, Suy, Yen, & Chhay, 2018), which can be achieved through the leadership style (s) adopted. As far as the healthcare environment is concerned, leaders and their style of leadership are very important in institutional performance. The healthcare environment basically deals with clients of diverse nature, who play different roles towards the achievement of goals. The healthcare environment described as turbulent, presents a challenging situation and therefore the need for an appropriate leadership style (s) (Alharbi & Yusoff, 2012).

In Ghana, there has been an increasing public demand for improved healthcare delivery in various healthcare facilities within the country. This can be achieved through the appropriate leadership styles practiced in the hospitals. Essentially, the form of leadership style determines the organization's performance. This is because the leaders' style of directing the use of resources, guiding members to implement strategies, and convincing members of the organization to work towards expected outcomes will shape the performance of the organization and the staff. (Aberese-Ako, Agyepong, & Dijk, 2018). Productivity and efficiency scores in several hospitals in Ghana have shown that organizational performances in hospitals are generally very low (Ministry of Health, 2007). Studies conducted on district hospitals in Ghana indicate that about 56.2% out of 128 hospitals recorded efficiency scores below average (0.50) (Novignon & Nonvignon, 2017). Also, the low productivity in the health sector is backed by the World Bank Health Worker Productivity report, which indicates that in regions, districts and cadres in Ghana, the results of low performance are the low standards of care recorded for clients (Saleh, 2013).

Moreover, factors like inadequate resources and inaccessibility of health facility explain the low performance of healthcare organizations. Leadership style is another significant factor that this research examines (Aberese –Ako, Agyepong & Dijk, 2018). Even though various researches have been conducted on leadership style and job performance little can be associated with the Health sector of Ghana hence the need for this research to assess the effect of leadership styles on job performance in the health sector of Ghana. This study contributes to closing the gap in literature determining the relationship between leadership style and Hospital performance, by focusing on the Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba (TSHW). The rest of the study is structured as follows: Section two provides a review of the relevant literature on the subject matter. Section three discusses the methodology used in the study. Section four analyzes the results. Section five discusses the findings of the study and finally section six concludes and makes recommendations for policy and practice.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Leadership

Academics and practitioners have attempted over the years to ascertain the concept of leadership, bringing to bear a set of traits an individual owns to influence other people in a situation to act or obey their desired manner (Alharbi & Yusoff, 2012). Again, Ghiasipour (2017) started that leadership as a long-term process of persuading people toward accomplishing a mission or goals of an organization. He further indicates that the process includes setting aims and strategies, enhancing commitment, ensuring compliance to set goals and objectives and productivity, and also promoting the culture of teamwork and acceptance of dynamic ideas and methods.

Leadership is also seen as the process by which individuals' effectiveness is amplified, while sustaining, if not increasing motivation, work satisfaction and other forms of psychological well-being' (Asamani, 2015). These indicate that a leader can be described as someone who has the capability to lead his employees and direct their behaviour. Leadership is exhibited by individuals by their talents and abilities, and is very important for all organizations especially in realizing set goals and performance. Having considered the countless concept of leadership, the common elements of leadership include the fact that it is a process, and the core responsibility of leaders are influencing others, especially junior colleagues to achieve expected targets of the institution or organization. It however expressed in different styles and indicated in the next sections.

2.2. Leadership Styles

The nature of humans and the environment they find themselves have led to various leadership styles being espoused by researchers (Beakana, 2017). The various leadership styles; thus autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles. Thus, beyond this, other styles such as the transformational, transactional, participative, instrumental and supportive leadership styles have emerged.

Autocratic Leadership Style:

This leadership style can be seen as one where leaders instruct their employees on what to do. Employees are told what to do, and therefore act in accordance with what they are told to do. Also, such leader could be seen as self-centered, and the leader makes decisions concerning the organization. Additionally, employees and subordinates are supervised more closely (Vliert, 2016).

The Democratic Leadership Style:

The democratic leadership style was stipulated by White (2000), and has been defined to induce 'group involvement, dialogue, and group decision encouraged by the leader' (Choi, 2007). This positions the democratic leadership style as the direct opposite of the autocratic leadership style. The democratic leaders consult with employees or subordinates, and seek their opinions in order to make decisions concerning the organization. As the name suggests, there is an open access by all employees to feel free in making decisions and partaking in the decision-making process. However, the democratic leadership style can be problematic if time required to achieve a goal is stretched or extended due to the laxity in operations.

Laissez-faire leadership Style:

This form of leadership style has been defined as one that allows employees or subordinates to work independently. Therefore the leader does not interfere with the work of subordinates, however, there is room for consultation when needed (Malcolm & Tamatey, 2017). The leader plays a key role by providing all the needed resources, but gives the employees or staffs the rights and the powers of making decisions to do their work and also to attain the goals of the organization. It has been explained by (Beakana, 2017) that, for the laissez-faire leadership style to work perfectly, the culture of the organization must be one that promotes commitment and loyalty. Also the organizational culture must ensure that employees have the requisite skills and be experienced or at best, be specialists in their field. Leaders who use this style must perform the task of effectively monitoring their employees and measuring their performance without interfering with their work.

Transactional Leadership Style:

This form leadership style has three elements including contingent reward, management-by-exception (active form) and management-by-exception (passive form). The use of this leadership style entails the leader identifying an obligatory change, creating a vision to direct the change by inspiring others, and gradually effects the change with the effort of members of his group (Thuijsman, 2015). A transactional leader uses rewards to achieve organizational performance, and appreciates good performance. The problem with the transactional leadership style is that it may prevent creativity amongst employees and also decrease job satisfaction.

Transformational Leadership Style:

This form of leadership style has to do with developing staff or subordinates while attending to their needs. It is a style where, "one or more persons engage with others in such a way that leaders and followers raise one another to higher levels of motivation and morality." Transformational leaders are therefore concerned with the growth and development of their employees or subordinates and their value systems (Vliert, 2016). Transformational leaders have the 'ability to overcome organizational and individual limitations. Thus, they push their subordinates to achieve more than they set out to achieve. Employees are encouraged to do more to overcome and go beyond intended goals.

Participative Leadership Style:

By the use of this leadership style, leaders involve employees on diverse levels of the process of making decisions as well as taking action in order to accomplish intended goals of the organization (Nemaiei, 2012). In other words, participative leaders take into consideration the views and concerns of their subordinates, as well as their values and include them in attaining organizational goals. Participative leaders are endowed with consultative manners and therefore consult subordinates for ideas before making a definitive decision, although, they retain final decision authority.

Instrumental Leadership Style:

The instrumental leadership is concerned mostly with the tiniest details in achieving organizational goals. The instrumental leader pays particular attention to the 'whats' and 'hows' of leadership and finding out or dealing with any details that may be concerned with achieving organizational goals. It is asserted by Rowold (2014) that there are two main dimensions to the instrumental leadership style. These include strategic leadership, which involves environmental monitoring to understand the environment of the organization, as well as the limits and delimits of the environment, and how it can fully be utilized. Strategy formulating and implementing is also done in this dimension to achieve organizational goals. The second dimension involves the facilitation of work, where workers tasks are clarified for them, resources and information are provided, and effective monitoring is done, all in the bid to make workers achieve goals of the organization.

Supportive Leadership Style:

This type of leadership style is one that enhance a positive organizational environment. It is the culminated character and steps taken by leaders to provide employees with the necessary assistance that they need in order to work effectively and be productive. Supportive leadership involves leaders going the extra mile to make work satisfying for followers and also treating followers in the same way and respecting their position (Northouse, 2016).

3. Empirical Literature Review

This empirical review focused on leadership in hospital organizations and their impact on organizational performance.

Leadership in Health Organizations

In a study by Tate (2004) at William Harvey Hospital in Ashford, Kent, where a considerable number of 30 women patients were maimed as a result of the hospital's culture where consultants were highly valued over other workers, and junior staff were afraid of reporting the truth about activities in the hospital. The findings of the study indicated the consultants were the ones directing the affairs of the hospital which was affecting the growth of William Harvey Hospital.

A similar study by Beakana (2017) which focused primarily on nursing leadership at Kenzie's City Hospital. This study examined the intensive care department of the hospital for the reason that different cases are reported with different levels of severity. They recognized that the right or effective leadership is needed in order that the best results can be achieved. Recognizing the critical nature of the health environment, (Maboko, 2011) suggests that managers in the health sector, specifically nursing managers need to learn about other recent leadership styles like the transformational and visionary leadership styles. These he believes are more suitable for a hospital setting, than the use of autocratic leadership style used by nursing management in the hospital where the research was carried out.

Also, in recognizing the relevance of hospital leadership in playing a role in the administration of hospitals and for achieving expected outcomes, Kowalski (2017) examined the importance of leadership in preventing healthcare-associated infection. By examining leadership styles used in fourteen (14) hospitals in the United States, it was established that those performing well, cultivated a culture of clinical excellence. This culture was made known to all staff, overcame barriers and dealt with staff who resisted leadership or factors that obstructed prevention, motivated their subordinates to work, and also introduced strategies that would eventually lead to the success of the organization. Thus, successful hospital leadership meant a combination of multi-faceted practices.

Further studies have shown that effective leadership equally enhances greater work satisfaction and performance (Ahmad, 2013; Namusonge, & Iravo, 2016). This study adopted descriptive design and used a stratified sampling technique to select 384 employees from level five hospital as well as Kenyatta National Hospital was part of the study. Findings from the study revealed that poor relationship between leaders and their subordinates influence the performance of Kenya health sector. This research forms the basis of understanding clearly the link between leadership styles used and the effect it can have on the job performance of employees and the facility in general. Prior to this Kenyan study by Namusonge, & Iravo, 2016, Asamani (2015) had carried out a study in relation to leadership styles adopted by nurse managers and also determine the influence of Nurse Managers' leadership on Nurses' perceived productivity level. This identified diverse leadership styles to be employed based on the situations. The prominent leadership styles identified to be practiced by nurse managers included supportive leadership style, achievement-oriented leadership style, participative leadership style and directive leadership in chronological order. Also, the only leadership style that accounted for variance in perceived productivity level was achievement-oriented leadership style.

4. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Model on Leadership styles and organizational performance

Source: Adapted from the main components of Path-Goal Theory (Northouse, 2016).

As depicted in Figure 1, the conceptual framework explains the connection that exist between leadership styles and organizational performance or outcomes represented by worker cooperation, inspiration to work, quality of performance, extra effort and productivity. The dependent variables in this framework are employee cooperation, inspiration to work, quality of performance, extra effort and productivity, whilst leadership style is the independent variable. Leadership styles may direct influence on performance. Considering the diverse opinions on the influence of leadership styles in the performance of hospitals, this current study seeks to ascertain which leadership style is highly practiced and impacts on performance of a critical care giving health facility like the Trauma and Specialist Hospital in Ghana. This was done using the following methods.

5. Methodology

This section presents an overview of the study, the method of data collection and the method of data analysis.

5.1. Research setting

The aim, design and setting of the study

The paper aims to examine the link between leadership styles and organizational performance at the Trauma and Specialist Hospital in Ghana. Primary data were sourced from the field of study through questionnaire administration. The researchers sought for permission from the municipal directorate of health to engage with employees of Trauma and Specialist Hospital within the municipality. A written permission was granted. At the preparatory stage, the questionnaires designed were tested to make sure participants understood the demands of the questions in the questionnaires.

5.2. Research Approach

The study adopted the quantitative research design to collect data and answer research questions pertaining to the effect of leadership styles on staff performance. Quantitative data is employed especially as a result of the large number of respondents, and because the research problem involved using questionnaires to assess the link between leadership styles and the organization's performance.

5.3. Research Design

Cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study. Cross-sectional survey allows the researcher to use the questionnaire to examine diverse variables at the same time.

5.4. Population

The population for this study made up of all the staff of the Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba (TSHW) totaling 216 full-time employees.

5.5. Sampling and sampling size

In all 216 respondents were selected using purposive sampling and simple random. The purposive sampling was used to select the various heads of the units in the hospital while simple random was used to select other employees. A modified structured Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) 5X propounded by Bass and Avolio (1997) was used. Questionnaires were administered to staff. Items in the questionnaire were close ended with some on three and four-point Likert-scale. How was performance measured please? It not so clear the time interval for assessing the leadership styles (is it that all these different styles were occurring concurrently or at different times?). I'm asking because you examining different leadership styles in the same organization. What were the indicators for performance within the stipulated period(s)? Please call me when you are free so we discuss.

5.6. Data Analysis

The data collected was sorted, edited, cleaned and coded to ensure accuracy and clarity before they are analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Service Solutions) version 20 for descriptive statistics for the objectives while to test the hypotheses, inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment correlation was used.

5.7. Ethical Considerations

Permission was sought from management of the hospital as well as the individuals that were used for the study. Approval was also sought from the deputy director in charge of division of human resources through an introductory letter collected from the University of Ghana, Legon to introduce the researcher to the hospital and the heads of the various departments/units within the hospital. The consent of the staff was sought through their respective superiors and the purpose and objective of the study were communicated to them. Respondents were

encouraged respond objectively and that was also told it was not mandatory to partake. They were therefore allowed to withdraw their consent at any time and without any form of adverse consequence.

6. Analysis of Results

This chapter presents analysis of the data as well as the findings and divided into three broad sections; general demographic and work experience of the respondents, dominant leadership style in the facility, relationship between Leadership style dimension and Organizational Performance, and the overall findings of the data is presented.

6.1. Demographics and work Experience

For the researcher to know the leadership styles practiced at the hospital, respondent working experience and number of years worked at the hospital were examined. Data gathered indicating that 76 (35.2%) had 1 – 5 years working experience. The second highest numbers of respondents, 64 (29.6%) had between 11 – 15 years working experience. Again, 42 (19.4%) had 6-10years working experience while 34 (15.7%) had 16-20 years working experience.

6.2. Leadership style that is dominant at the hospital

This section sought to find out the dominant leadership style used at the hospital and whether it should be encouraged.

Table 1: Leadership Styles

	Frequency	Percent
Transformational leadership	18	8.3%
Transactional leadership	34	15.8%
Participative Leadership	64	29.6%
Supportive Leadership	48	22.2%
Instrumental Leadership	52	24.1%

Source: Field Data, 2020.

(N = 216)

The findings revealed that the most dominant leadership style used at Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba (TSHW) was the Participative leadership style where 64 (29.6%) of respondent revealed that it was frequently, if not always used. The second most used leadership style was the instrumental leadership style which had 52 (24.1%) as indicated by respondent. Again, supportive leadership had 48 (22.2%) while transactional leadership 34 (15.8%).

Table 2: Relationship between Leadership style dimension and Organizational Performance

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
Organizational Performance	3.1505	.53390	1					
Transformational Leadership	2.8674	.61008	.442**	1				
Transactional Leadership	2.4329	.58087	.248**	.460**	1			
Participative Leadership Style	2.9941	.76561	.445**	.718**	.327**	1		
Supportive Leadership Style	3.1299	.74206	.443**	.718**	.331**	.720**	1	
Instrumental Leadership Style	3.1726	.65733	.406**	.679**	.280**	.699**	.709**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result shows correlations between the following leadership styles; transformational, transactional, participative, supportive, instrumental and organizational performance. Correlation among them is as follows; transformational leadership (.442**), transactional leadership (.248**) participative leadership (.445**), Supportive

Leadership (.443**) and Instrumental Leadership (.406**). They all have some significant correlation with organizational performance. The findings show that leadership styles used had positive and significant influence on the organizational performance of Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba.

7. Discussion

The first objective sought to find out the dominant leadership style used at the hospital and whether it should be encouraged. The findings revealed that the most dominant leadership style used at Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba (TSHW) was the Participative leadership style. The results indicate that leaders at the hospital should ensure that responsibilities are shared and also delegated by including everyone. In addition, to ensure participation of all employees, continual consultation on major issues and decisions are done together with the staff, even though the leaders have the final say. Despite Participative leadership style being the most used, the findings also support other findings that have argued or indicated that managers or unit heads use several leadership styles depending on persisting conditions (Asamani, 2015). That is, the participative leadership style is also the dominant style exhibited by management and unit heads at TSHW. Therefore, the participative leadership style is frequently used by leaders at TSHW, and also has a greater effect on performance than the other leadership styles assessed. What this means is that, leaders at the TSHW consult with their subordinates for ideas and alternative measures before taking any ultimate decision. Additionally, they share responsibilities amongst their subordinates by involving them in preparatory, decision-making as well as implementation stages of the work in order for the hospital as an organization to perform (Lumbasi, K'Aol, & Ouma, 2016).

The second objective was to find out the relationship between Leadership style and Organizational Performance. The findings show that leadership styles used had positive and significant influence on the organizational performance of Trauma and Specialist Hospital, Winneba. These findings are in line with earlier studies showing the substantial relationship that exist between leadership styles and organizational performance (Khajeh, 2018; Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa, & Nwankwere, 2011). This finding also confirms the views of Blanchard and Hersey (2006) on situational approaches to leadership. This leadership model proposes that there is no single approach to leadership, and the type of leadership used becomes necessary depending on the situation (Gachingiri, 2015).

8. Conclusion/Implications

The study focused on the effect of leadership styles on organizational performance at TSHW. It primarily focuses was on the five leadership styles thus, the Transformational, Transactional, Participative, Instrumental and Supportive leadership styles. The study revealed that all the forms of leadership styles had a positive effect on organizational performance. However, the participative form of leadership has a greater influence on performance at TSHW.

Since the participative leadership is recognized as the leadership style that achieves very high organizational performance, it is suggested that it should be maintained at the TSHW. The implication is that, the organization would survive and achieve the goals of the organization if the leaders continue to use the participative leadership style, where management and unit heads continue to motivate staff by their continuous inclusion of employees in preparation and decision making process as well as they using their skills to go beyond expected performance.

9. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, it is recommended that:

1. Leaders at TSHW should consider seriously the use of the participative leadership behaviours at TSHW. Even though leaders have used the transformational, transactional, instrumental and supportive leadership styles at TSHW, the participative leadership style has proved more worthwhile and influenced significantly the performance at TSHW, and must be considered above others.
2. The management at the TSHW must be able to have a balance between the styles of leadership they use to reflect their interest of development of their subordinates equally, so as to enhance and grow the organizations performance. Simply put leaders must give equal attention to getting work done, and

keeping the subordinates happy or satisfied.

3. Feedback on performance on regular basis should be encourage across all management levels of the hospital. This would ensure the regular feedback indicating how leadership styles are affecting the performance of the organization and direct which procedures should be used to ensure the continuous positive performance of the organization.

Well done. Just put back the areas you removed and only be careful not to exceed 7000words overall.
Thanks

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